

Magical Realism in Toni Morrison's *Beloved*

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Abstract

Magical realism is a literary technique that establishes a link between the conventional realm of realism in literature and the inclusion of extraordinary aspects inside a work of art. Magical realism endeavors to imbue a literary composition set in a realistic milieu with fantastical, unusual, and otherworldly qualities. On one side, the symbolic aspect of an artistic creation elucidates the intricacies of quotidian existence. Conversely, it employs the use of magic as a means to enhance the authenticity of reality. Numerous authors employ this literary approach to interrogate the nature of the tangible realm, elucidate the anxieties or aspirations of their characters, and scrutinize the historical context of the realistic domain. The literary work authored by Toni Morrison, titled "*Beloved*," serves as a profound examination of African-American history, the repercussions of trauma, and the lasting consequences of the institution of slavery. The work exhibits a notable feature in the form of magical realism, a literary device that amalgamates parts of the fantastical with realistic portrayals of locations and characters. In the novel *Beloved*, Morrison adeptly utilizes the literary technique of magical realism to enhance the reader's comprehension of the characters' encounters and to communicate the intricate dynamics between individual and communal recollections. This research aims to explore the significance of magical realism in the novel *Beloved*, focusing on its role in enhancing the thematic

elements and overall impact of the work. Toni Morrison's novel *Beloved* has been widely regarded as a representation of magic realism in literature. However, there exists a counterargument among certain reviewers who contend that *Beloved* does not align with the characteristics typically associated with magical realism. The present study centers on the intersection of magic and realism within the context of African-American history, with a particular focus on the theme of trauma stemming from the institution of slavery.

Introduction

This section provides an overview of the topic at hand. It introduces the main concepts and objectives of the study, setting the inquiry to the definition and significance of the literary genre known as magical realism. Magical realism is a peculiar paradox that combines two divergent elements, denoting the convergence of realism and fantasy within artistic expression, cinematic productions, and literary works. The work effectively integrates parts of realism with the fantastical, seamlessly incorporating magical components that naturally emerge from the depicted reality (Standish, 1995, pp. 156-157).

The Hispanic culture of South America encompasses the literary genre known as magical realism. This genre is characterized by works of fiction that blur the boundaries between realistic and non-realistic events. In magical realism, supernatural, mythical, or implausible elements are seamlessly integrated into the cognitive framework of reality without causing a perceptible disruption in the narrator's or the character's consciousness (Standish, 1995, pp. 156-157).

In the context of magical realism, characters within the book are depicted as encountering magical and fantastical elements with a level of acceptance equivalent to their encounters with settings and individuals

typically associated with "reality" and "fact." The term "magical realist" was first introduced by German art historian Franz Roh in 1925. Roh used the term "Magischer Realismus" to describe a style of painting that emerged after the Expressionist movement. This style blended elements of realism with a focus on conveying the extraordinary aspects of reality (Roh, 1925, p. 60). In Roh's essay on Karl Haider's paintings, the phrase "magical realism" is introduced as an aesthetic art category that visually conveys the enigmatic aspects of reality. The prevailing scholarly agreement, however, attributes the establishment of the connection between Latin American writing and the phenomena known as "lo real maravilloso" to Alejo Carpentier, a Cuban novelist who was exiled. In his seminal essay titled "On the Marvelous Real in America" (Carpentier, 1995, pp. 75-88), Carpentier aimed to establish a clear distinction between Latin American magical realism and European Surrealism. He emphasized the divergence between the arbitrary and even contrived manipulation of reality found in the works of Surrealists and the organic portrayal of the Latin American worldview in the concept of "lo real maravilloso." Carpentier argued that magical realism reflected a prevalent understanding in the Caribbean, Central, and South America of a more fluid boundary between the real and the fantastical, which differed from the prevailing beliefs in North America and Europe.

Magical realism in the Americas has been associated with indigenous and black Weltanschauungen worldviews rooted in the myths and legends of cultures with a foundation in ritualistic religious practices. Brenda Cooper, a postcolonial scholar, elucidates that magical realism emerges within specific societies characterized by postcolonialism and uneven development, where the coexistence of old and new, modern and ancient, and scientific and magical perspectives on the world is prevalent (Cooper, 1998, p. 216).

The notion that magical realism arises out of those colonial and postcolonial moments which create a considerable population of subjects whose interests may be counter-hegemonic, explains the contradiction between the relative absence of magical realist texts produced in Europe – and by Euro-American writers in Canada and the United States – and the growing proliferation of such texts in Africa, Asia, and Latin America – and among European, Canadian, and U.S. authors of African, Asian, and Latin descent. As a discourse and worldview of cultural difference and resistance to domination, magical realism reorganizes the elements of hegemonic paradigms, investing them with new, expanded meanings. Magical realism realizes the hybridization of the natural and the supernatural by focusing on specific historical moments to problematize present-day disjunctive realities. It is a form of writing characterized by a dual character: an inward doubleness - the natural and the supernatural - which reflects an outward direction toward (post)colonial cultural relations through revisionary memory (Walter, 1999, p. 4).

2. Section Two

2.1. Morrison's Biography

Toni Morrison, originally named Chloe Anthony Wofford, was born in 1931 and spent her early years in Ohio. She obtained a bachelor's degree in English from Howard University and completed a master's program at Cornell University. Due to difficulties encountered by her peers in pronouncing her uncommon given name, she opted to change it to Toni, derived from her middle name. In 1958, Morrison entered into matrimony with Harold Morrison, an architect hailing from Jamaica, and the couple bore two sons. However, their marriage concluded in divorce after six

years. Following her pursuit of an academic career, during which she taught English at Howard University, Morrison transitioned into an editorial role at Random House, where she specialized in the field of Black fiction (Walter, 1999, p. 4).

At the same time, she began building a body of creative work that, in 1993, would make her the first African-American woman to receive the Nobel Prize for Literature. Morrison's first novel, *The Bluest Eye*, was not an immediate success, but she continued to write. *Sula*, which appeared in 1973, was more successful, earning a nomination for the National Book Award. In 1977, *Song of Solomon* launched Morrison's national reputation, winning her the National Book Critics' Circle Award. Her most well-known work, *Beloved*, appeared in 1987 and won the Pulitzer Prize. Her other novels include *Tar Baby* (1981), *Jazz* (1992), and *Paradise* (1998).

Meanwhile, Morrison returned to teaching and was a professor at Yale and the State University of New York at Albany. Today, she is the Robert F. Goheen Professor in the Council of Humanities at Princeton University, where she teaches creative writing. In 1993, Morrison became the first African-American woman to receive the Nobel Prize in literature. (Ibid.) Morrison expressed her desire to contribute to forming a canon of Black literature, highlighting the unfortunate reality that Black writers often feel compelled to cater to a white readership rather than being able to focus solely on their craft. Numerous readers perceive Morrison's novels as significant strides toward realizing her envisioned literary tradition. In her work *Beloved*, Morrison employs a poetic and refined writing style that does not seek to appease any particular audience. Instead, she challenges readers, urging them to embrace her work on her terms (Lobodaziec, 3).

2.2. The Presence of Magical Realism in Toni Morrison's *Beloved*

In the novel *Beloved*, Morrison presents the narrative of the character Sethe. Sethe is an African-American woman who fulfills the role of a mother to four offspring. Sethe successfully emancipates herself and her offspring from the institution of slavery, harboring a genuine aspiration to secure their liberation from the oppressive system. In an act of maternal sacrifice, the protagonist takes her daughter's life, Beloved, to liberate her from the oppressive institution of slavery. After eight years, the daughter is resurrected in the spectral manifestation. According to the source, Beloved's apparition commenced haunting the residence. According to the source provided (www.grad/belo), Sethe's two sons, Howard and Buglar, flee from the residence after experiencing particularly distressing encounters with the apparition. One of the individuals who arrived at 124 was a female named Beloved. Subsequently, Sethe possesses unwavering certainty over her maternal relationship with her daughter. The spectral manifestation of Beloved serves as a symbolic embodiment of Sethe's traumatic experiences during her enslavement, encapsulating her enduring psychological distress and apprehension associated with this period of her life. The recollection pursued her with the same intensity as that of a ghost. Consequently, Sethe has valuable insight into the significance of reconciling with her previous experiences and directing her focus toward the future.

A characteristic element of magic realism in a literary composition involves situating the narrative within an ostensibly commonplace reality imbued with recognizable historical and cultural contexts (OPR/OPRA, n.d.). In the novel *Beloved*, the depiction of the reality of slavery is presented as commonplace. Moreover, Sethe's pursuit of the desired state of freedom compels her to engage in behaviors not readily explicable by universally accepted principles or familiar logical reasoning (www.opr/opra). The act of taking the life of one's daughter to protect her

from a life of enslavement serves as an illustration of such behaviors. Another instance of such behaviors can be observed when Sethe endeavors to disclose her narrative to Paul D. (Lobodaziec, 3).

The woman was engaged in rotational motion. She was circularly moving within the confines of the space. Beyond the jelly cupboard, the window, and the front door lie another window, followed by the sideboard, the entrance to the keeping room, the dry sink, and the stove, ultimately leading back to the jelly cupboard. Paul D positioned himself at the table, seeing her gradual emergence into his field of vision, only to vanish from sight as she rotated like a deliberate, unhurried wheel. The fragmentation observed in Sethe's activities reflects the socio-cultural context in which she resides. Due to her apprehension of enslavement, she is compelled to relocate frequently throughout various locations. The novel's background highlights an additional characteristic of magic realism, wherein the items and places depicted can assume autonomous existence, a phenomenon perceived as commonplace by the characters inside the narrative (source: www.opr/opra). The above characteristic is sometimes called the "method of incorporating the supernatural" (Lobodaziec, 7). The phenomenon occurs when the characters perceive exceptional events or circumstances as commonplace, primarily due to the absence of optimism and transformation within their lived reality. The acknowledgment of the exceptional prompts individuals to contemplate the concept of "supernatural phenomena" (Ibid) as a component of ordinary existence (Ibid). In the novel *Beloved*, the characters navigate and confront supernatural occurrences as an integral component of their everyday existence. According to Lobodaziec (8), Sethe and Dunk demonstrate a seemingly mundane act by returning the sideboard, which had been displaced by the ghost, to its initial position. The integration of supernatural elements becomes evident when female community members

discuss Beloved's reappearance from the realm of the deceased as an entirely ordinary occurrence (Ibid). In the following conversation, the integration above and acknowledgment demonstrates that the apparition possesses corporeal attributes, such as the ability to consume sustenance and beverages and engage in slumber. Therefore, the apparition engages in social interactions with individuals within the realm of typical human behavior.

The individual in question is named Ella. What is the current discourse surrounding Sethe that I have been hearing? Please inform me whether it is present with her. The extent of my knowledge is limited to the information provided. Is the individual being referred to the daughter? Is the individual in question deceased? That is the information provided to me." "What evidence supports their claim of her identity? The object is currently in a stationary position. The individual engages in activities such as sleeping, consuming food, and engaging in disruptive behavior. Engaging in the act of subjecting Sethe to daily whippings. /"I am astonished." Is there an infant present? No. The concept of "grown" refers to the process of maturation and development in individuals or the chronological stage that the subject would have reached had it continued to exist. /"Are you referring to the physical body? "I am referring to the topic of human anatomy." "Are you suggesting the act of physically disciplining her? The source, as mentioned earlier, is being referenced again.

Another defining element of magic realism is the narrative's ability to immerse the reader in a perplexing and labyrinthine experience as the plot gradually unfolds (OPR/OPRA, n.d.). The presence of fragmented narrators, unforeseen happenings, and the perplexing behavior of characters engender a sense of confusion among readers, rendering it difficult for them to anticipate forthcoming acts. Furthermore, as the plot

progresses, the reader can access additional facts and specifics about a particular character's narrative. Passages represent a distinctive element within the realm of magic realism. This trait suggests that certain characters possess a mystical understanding of forthcoming events, according to Lobodaziec (8). On one side, a character's expectations indicate the prevailing reality surrounding said character. Conversely, possessing foreknowledge of forthcoming events illuminates the mystical component inside the literary composition. Baby Suggs anticipated the arrival of darkness, which she perceived as an elusive presence concealed by another scent (Ibid). This occurs when the schoolteacher arrives at 124 searching for Sethe and her children. However, Sethe resists by engaging in an act of "attempting to kill her children" (Ibid). The apparition of a deceased child, Beloved, is regarded as the primary manifestation of magical realism in Morrison's novel, *Beloved*. The primary objective of the ghost's presence is to facilitate a process of experiential rebirth. The characters in the novel *Beloved* experience the harrowing effects of slavery, as the resurrection of the ghost catalyzes the resurfacing of their traumatic history. According to Dr. N. Seraman, the reappearance of *Beloved* as a ghost serves to reintroduce the lingering effects of historical slavery, allowing Morrison to confront the violent legacy of this institution (Seraman 2). Morrison establishes a connection between the spectral presence of *Beloved* and the historical tragedy of "Sixty Million and More ."This numerical value pertains to the mortality rate of around sixty million enslaved individuals. Morrison explains this numerical value.

According to certain historians, the estimated death toll amounts to 200 million individuals. The minimum value reported by any individual was 60 million. Numerous trip narratives documented individuals' experiences in the Congo, whereby they reported encountering a significant obstacle in the form of an obstructed river passage due to the overwhelming presence

of deceased individuals. This situation can be likened to a logjam, wherein the flow of the river is impeded. A significant number of individuals perished. Fifty percent of the individuals perished on such vessels.

Approximately sixty million enslaved individuals perished along the course of the Congo River. According to (Seraman,2), *Beloved's* spirit united with a woman's deceased body aboard one of the ships. In the novel "*Beloved*," the protagonist recounts her harrowing encounter aboard a vessel dedicated to transporting enslaved individuals.

The individual consistently assumes a crouched position while the male figure nearby is deceased. Initially, there is a spatial separation between the female and male subjects, with storms causing a convergence and intermingling of the genders. Subsequently, the narrator finds themselves positioned on the posterior of the male figure, with limited visual access to only his neck and broad shoulders. The male individual maintains eye contact before expiring on the narrator's visage, unbeknownst to the others present.

The term "beloved" refers to the harrowing ordeal of the slave ship voyage. The individual experiences ongoing challenges till their demise. She drew a comparison between her tomb and the experience of enslavement. Denver inquired about the origin of her place of residence. In response, the character Beloved expressed that the environment below was characterized by darkness, intense heat, a lack of breathable air, and limited space for movement (Ibid). The depiction of Beloved's tombs serves as a poignant portrayal of the authentic lived reality of slavery. The tomb exhibits a somber hue akin to the slave vessel, whereby many individuals are densely packed, impeding her respiratory capacity. The cemetery is an exceptional component that accentuates the authenticity of the enslavement ordeal.

The utilization of magical realism in the novel *Beloved* obscures the demarcation between the corporeal and metaphysical realms. The figure of *Beloved*, who manifests as a spectral entity, epitomizes this amalgamation. She embodies both corporeal existence and a metaphysical being, symbolizing the enduring impact of enslavement. The ambiguity regarding the existence of the character *Beloved* contributes an additional element of enigma and symbolism to the narrative, prompting readers to contemplate the profound psychological and emotional ramifications of the institution of slavery—the utilization of magical realism inside the book functions as a potent mechanism for representing symbolism. An example can be seen in the character of Baby Suggs, who exhibits a prophetic capacity for engaging in communication with the spiritual realm as a formerly enslaved person. The author's ritualistic gatherings in the Clearing serve as a figurative realm where individuals can heal and experience spiritual revitalization. Morrison underscores the transformational efficacy of communal rituals and the enduring fortitude of the human spirit through the incorporation of supernatural elements throughout these scenes.

The use of magical realism serves as a means for Morrison to effectively communicate the tremendous psychological distress endured by the protagonists and the shared recollection of the institution of slavery. The author employs evocative and lyrical descriptions to effectively portray the characters' inner realms, aspirations, and recollections, thus creating a sense of ambiguity between historical events and the current narrative. This technique not only exemplifies the fractured character of memory but also underscores the lasting influence of historical trauma on individuals and societies.

The use of magical realism in the novel *Beloved* is a compelling departure from conventional historical narratives, as it introduces a more intricate and imaginative examination of African-American lived

experiences. The narrative structure employed by Morrison in her work deviates from traditional linear storytelling and challenges conventional perceptions of reality. This departure enables Morrison to explore the intricate psychological dimensions of her characters and portray the multifaceted nature of their lives. By incorporating supernatural elements within a historical context, the author offers a nuanced depiction of the African-American lived experience that transcends the limitations of conventional historical narratives.

CONCLUSIONS

In the novel *Beloved*, Toni Morrison skillfully exploits the literary technique of magical realism to produce a deep and thought-provoking exploration of the enduring impact of slavery and the intricate nature of African-American encounters. Morrison's narrative exhibits a propensity for blurring boundaries, employing symbolic resonance, expressing trauma and memory, and challenging historical narratives. This multifaceted approach engenders a complex and intricate literary experience that captivates readers, stimulating their intellectual and emotional faculties. The use of magical realism functions as a powerful literary mechanism that amplifies the thematic elements of the work and contributes to its enduring significance. *Beloved* serves as a tribute to the efficacy of literature in addressing challenging historical narratives and shedding light on the indomitable nature of the human psyche.

Beloved is a seminal example of the magic realism genre. Therefore, it has specific attributes commonly associated with this literary style and displays distinct traits of magical realism. The novel's setting exhibits characteristics of the literary genre known as magic realism. Commonplace historical and cultural circumstances characterize the environment. The occurrences inside the realm of magic realism sometimes elude explication by conventional universal principles or recognized logical frameworks.

Another notable aspect pertains to the technique employed for integrating the supernatural elements, whereby the unusual phenomena are perceived as commonplace from the perspective of the characters. The manifestation of unforeseen occurrences experienced by the reader as the narrative progresses constitutes a characteristic element of the literary genre known as magic realism. Ultimately, the spectral presence of the character *Beloved* serves to reveal the use of magical realism within *Beloved*.

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